

Continuous Evolution of The Unified Platform of Active Methodologies (PUMA): Focus on Integration between Market and Academia

Simone B. S. Monteiro¹, Rodrigo P. Gomes¹, Luis Guilherme B. Monteiro², Ana Cristina Fernandes Lima¹, Everaldo Silva Junior¹, Gabriel de Lanna Fiuza Curi Garcia³

¹ Pós-Graduação em Computação Aplicada, Darcy Ribeiro, Universidade de Brasília, Brasil.

² Engenharia de Software, Faculdade do Gama, Universidade de Brasília, Brasil.

³ Engenharia de Produção, Faculdade de Tecnologia, Universidade de Brasília, Brasil.

Email: simone_simao@yahoo.com.br, rodrpg23@yahoo.com.br, luisguilhermebm91@gmail.com, anacristina.limafernandes@gmail.com, everaldo.s.junior@gmail.com, gabriel.lanna@aluno.unb.br

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060898>

Abstract

The Unified Active Methodology Platform (PUMA) is a platform being developed by undergraduate students in Software Engineering and Design courses, with the participation of students and professors from Production Engineering and Applied Computing master's program at the University of Brasília. This project was supported by the Learning Program for the 3rd Millennium (A3M) in 2018, its conception year. Its focus is on capturing projects from various stakeholders and allocating them to Production Systems Projects disciplines, so that engineering students can present technological solutions. One of PUMA's objectives is to measure the effectiveness of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) methodology applied to the Production Engineering course at UnB, enabling students to acquire skills and knowledge necessary to meet market demands combined with academic knowledge. This article aims to present the continuous evolution of the PUMA Platform, focusing on updating functionalities and layouts implemented in its development process. The research has a qualitative approach and is classified as a case study. The results show that integration between different areas of knowledge is essential to ensure platform development, in order to find the needs of business managers and platform users.

Keywords: Active Methodologies; Problem Based Learning; Multidisciplinary; Project capture.

1 Introduction

The use of traditional teaching methodologies is employed by students in Higher Education Institutions, with the blackboard being the main tool for knowledge transmission, in which students transcribe the content into their notebooks. Over the years, a new approach of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has emerged, characterized by the dichotomy between theoretical formation and professional practice, as studied by Ponciano, Gomes, & Morais, (2017).

The curriculum of the Production Engineering (EPR) course at the University of Brasília (UnB) integrates into its innovative structure the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) method, which encompasses seven Production Systems Projects (PSP) disciplines. These disciplines are distributed throughout the student's academic trajectory, starting in the fourth semester and ending in the penultimate period of the course. The purpose of PBL is to encourage students to apply theoretical concepts of Production Engineering to solve concrete problems that arises from external stakeholders, promoting an integrated understanding between the demands of professional practice and the various areas of knowledge, facilitating the understanding of the variety of determining factors involved in solving challenges (Monteiro, Reis, Silva, & Souza, 2017).

The practical issues faced by organizations, regardless of whether they are in the private or public sector, large or small, active in industry or the service sector, serve as the basis for the topics addressed in the PSP disciplines. The main challenge is to identify these external stakeholders. To facilitate this process, the initial module of the

Unified Active Methodology Platform (PUMA) was developed, whose outline is described in the study by Monteiro, Campos, Lima, & Melo, (2018). This module focuses on automating the submission process of project proposals for PSP disciplines originating from real challenges faced by external stakeholders.

The Unified Active Methodology Platform (PUMA) originates from the Teaching Program for the Third Millennium (A3M) of the Distance Education Center (CEAD) of UNB and has been in development since then with the support of different multidisciplinary teams (Monteiro, Lima, Mariano, & Júnior, 2020). The platform features functionalities that assist in the process of capturing projects to be executed by students in the PSP disciplines of the Production Engineering course at the University of Brasília.

This study aims to present the continuous evolution of the PUMA Platform, focusing on updating the functionalities and layouts implemented in its development process, and is organized into five others sections, namely: the second section provides a literature review, covering current and relevant research fronts on the topic; the third section describes the methodology employed in the research, containing the methods used and their structuring; the fourth section details the results of the first module of PUMA, the implemented functionalities and the risks associated with its development; the fifth section shows students' views on the PUMA projects and the learning process; conclusions are finally presented in the sixth section.

2 Background and Related Works

In this section, relevant concepts underpinning the proposal of this study, along with similar research conducted, are addressed through a robust literature review.

2.1 PBL Approach (connecting projects to students)

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is an educational approach that prioritizes the use of real-world dilemmas to foster students' critical thinking development, promote problem-solving skills and facilitate the acquisition of knowledge about key concepts relevant to the area under analysis. These attributes contrast with traditional methods, which typically present a practical problem only after the exposition of theoretical content (de Andrade, dos Santos Jr. Pimentel, Bittencourt, & de Santana, 2010). Although originally developed for the medical course context, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has been adopted in various fields, including engineering. Successful experiences in implementing PBL in Engineering programs are evidenced, for example, in the Production Engineering course at the University of Brasília, Brazil, and in the Computer Engineering course at Aalborg University, Denmark (Betemps, Cechinel, & da Nóbrega Tavares, 2008). The literature describes a series of activities aimed at guiding students in identifying solutions to the problem (Gallagher, 2023). In this context, the approach is described in which a challenge is presented to students who, organized in groups, collaborate to analyze, define, and solve the problem based on their existing knowledge. Through discussions, students identify and record learning issues related to aspects of the problem they do not fully understand. Subsequently, the issues are prioritized by the group, and a plan is devised to investigate them, including who will be responsible, how, and when they will be addressed for future sharing. Upon gathering again, students explore the issues raised earlier, integrating new knowledge acquired into the context of the problem. At the end of the process, students participate in individual and collective assessments to develop self-assessment skills and provide constructive feedback to peers.

2.2 Benefits of implementing the PBL methodology

The current educational process is at a stage of operational exhaustion; and the rapid obsolescence of the vast array of knowledge transmitted to students fuels this debate. There is a consensus that conventional approaches no longer foster theoretical and practical learning nor encourage the cultivation of other forms of knowledge considered relevant in the academic, professional, and social spheres. However, even in the face of accepting the limitations of traditional models, higher education institutions are immersed in a crucial discussion: how to promote skills and attitudes for continuous and independent lifelong learning while facing the responsibility of teaching an increasing array of technical-scientific knowledge without overloading curricula or prolonging formal education (Cerqueira, Guimarães, & Noronha, 2016).

Like any educational method, PBL, despite its potential, presents risks, advantages, and disadvantages. The advantages identified in this approach include facilitating the acquisition of knowledge in a more lasting and meaningful way, as well as the development of professional skills and attitudes by students. These benefits seem to be consistent regardless of the implementation context, its structure, educational level, and field of study. According to studies conducted by Fernandes, Mesquita, Flores, & Lima, (2014), PBL encourages collaboration among students, promoting more intense communication among them and favoring the establishment of bonds not only among peers but also with teachers over time. Additionally, in this environment, students tend to take a more proactive stance when faced with unknown topics, seeking support for project development, and develop the ability to meet deadlines set by tutors and group members, aspects that reflect patterns observed in professional life (Gomes, Brito, & Varela, 2016).

2.3 Multidisciplinary in software development process

Over time, the evolution of software development practices has been evident. From the era of the waterfall model, characterized by sequential software construction, to contemporary agile methodologies, where software development is progressively iterative and incremental (Sommerville, 2011).

Current problem-solving approaches through Design Thinking (Panke, 2019) have been employed for requirement identification (Bernal, Raimondi, de Oliveira, Inoe, & Matsuda, 2018), providing significant contributions to development groups. The rapid development of minimum viable product prototypes (Caroli, 2015) to validate intermediate models together with agile software development methodologies (Schwaber, & Beedle, 2001) demands that professionals, predominantly from the computing field, demonstrate flexibility and multifunctional capability.

The article by Brauner, Janissek-Muniz, Granville, Moura, Fetter, & Nazar, (2017) describes the UFRGS 2016 App Challenge, an event with hackathon characteristics, organized with the purpose of integrating knowledge from students in Administration, Design, and Computing courses. The adopted methodology involved the formation of multidisciplinary teams, which faced the challenge of developing mobile applications over a weekend, covering prototyping, business modeling, and validation activities. The results show that multidisciplinary teams, adopting a product-centric approach, can contribute complementarity and collaboratively to application development.

The research conducted by Martins (2016) describes a successful multidisciplinary educational experience in a class of the fifth period of the Information Systems course at the Federal Institute of Goiás/Campus Luziânia. In this experience, students were engaged in software project development that integrated various disciplines in the same knowledge domain, offering a practical approach that served as a basis for future activities. This

work required the application of knowledge from disciplines such as Web Programming, Database, Software Engineering, Design Patterns, Requirements Analysis, and Human-Computer Interface.

3 Methodology

This study is an applied and qualitative research focused on the Unified Platform for Active Methodologies (PUMA). A survey was conducted with students to assess the strengths and areas for improvement of the development process, as well as the learning experience. The project receives funding from Foundation of Research Support for the Federal District (FAP-DF), a research support foundation in the Federal District. The development team consists of 15 individuals, including 9 developers, 1 designer, 1 lead technician, 1 quality assurance specialist and 3 platform creators (product owners). Ten team members participated in the research, including 8 developers, 1 Scrum Master and 1 designer.

A survey was conducted through a form with 10 questions. For data collection, a 5-point Likert scale was used, that is, two extremes, two intermediates, and a neutral opinion. Therefore, from 1 (Poor or Does not contribute or Strongly disagree) to 5 (Excellent or Contributes significantly or Strongly agree). To analyze the answers, pie charts were created, which allow visualization of responses on the Likert scale. The questions were divided into five categories: 1) software development process, 2) agile rites used in the project, 3) clickup for task management, 4) learning process, and 5) team integration.

The research progressed through several stages. The first stage outlines the development process of the PUMA platform, while the second stage examines its current state. The final stage presents the results of the student survey.

4 Results

The process for developing the PUMA platform adopts a hybrid methodology, with Agile as its main method. This section presents the process of developing and shows the main screens of PUMA.

4.1 PUMA platform development process

The development process comprised ten steps followed by students and professors respectively from Software Engineering and Production Engineering at the University of Brasília (UnB), as illustrated in Figure 1, which delineates the workflow during the research.

In the discovery (Step 1), the Product Owners, Scrum Master, and UX/UI Designer focused on understanding the needs (Step 2), which served as inputs for creating prototypes (Step 3). Visual representations of interfaces were crucial for defining the requirements (Step 4), along with acceptance criteria and business rules. Subsequently, the development team participated in planning meetings (Step 5) to prioritize tasks and estimate the effort required for each functionality. During the development (step 6), functionalities were coded and tested (step 7) interactively to ensure they met the established requirements. Following this, all software components were accepted (Step 8) by platform creators (product owners) after a business valuation. The retrospective (Step 9), or retro, is a structured meeting for reviewing the work done and the development process, highlighting takeaways and action plans to improve results. Additionally, team members held daily stand-up meetings (Step 10) to discuss their progress, plans, and any obstacles they encountered.

Figure 1. PUMA platform development process

4.2 Results of the screens developed in Epic 1

The figures two to eight depict the functionalities developed during the first epic.

Figure 2.a Functionality "PUMA Home screen - general" Figure 2.b Functionality "PUMA Home screen - public notice"

The Figures 2.a and 2.b show the homepage developed, the platform has four subsections, each one with a specific topic about the platform. They are: i) about the platform; ii) public notice; iii) learn more about PBL and iv) contacts.

Figure 3.a Functionality "Login" screen

Figure 3.b Functionality " User Sign in "screen

The Figures 3.a and 3.b show the login page, where the user can recover your password or Sign in to the platform.

Figure 4. Functionality "My Projects" screen

Figure 5. Functionality "Proposal Evaluation" screen

Figures 4 and 5 show the functionalities "My Projects" where the user can see the projects that were submitted or the ones being developed. "Proposal Evaluation" is a functionality where the professors can read and evaluate the project's proposals as accepted or denied.

Figure 6. Functionality "Keep up with Projects"

Figure 7. Functionality "Disciplines"

Figures 6 and 7 showcase the functionalities "Keep up with Projects" and "Disciplines." The first one focuses on keeping up with the projects. Once projects are accepted, they will be displayed on this screen, showing the discipline associated with the project and the professor who accepted it. The second figure illustrates the Disciplines functionality, where teachers can log in to courses and view disciplines offered by other teachers.

Figure 8 displays the "Project proposal submission", where the projects are submitted. Either by professors, students or external stakeholders.

Figure 8. Functionality "Project proposal submission"

5 Students' view of the PUMA project and the learning process

The survey was carried out using a form that covered the following categories: software development process, agile rites used in the project, clickup for task management, learning process, team integration, positive points of the PUMA project and suggestions for improvements and additional comments, as shown in figures nine to twelve. Figure 9 illustrates students' perspectives on aspects of the software engineering process.

Figure 9. students' perspectives on aspects of the software engineering process.

The analysis of the survey reveals an overall positive picture in the development process of the PUMA project, with aspects such as User Experience/User Interface (UX/UI) design being well rated by the team. However, areas of opportunity were also identified, such as the requirements gathering process, software development, testing, and quality, where the team expressed different levels of satisfaction and perception. Figure 10 illustrates the student's perspective on the aspects of rituals and tools.

Figure 10. Illustrates the student's perspective on the aspects of rituals and tools.

Regarding agile practices and learning, the analysis reveals a predominantly positive scenario. Most participants rated the effectiveness of agile practices, the usefulness of the daily meeting, and the relevance of

6 Conclusion

The goal of this study was achieved, that is, the recent results obtained in the PUMA development process were presented, highlighting the functionalities, along with their screens. Following agile practices, the complete development process consists of multiple cycles, rather than a single sequential process. This continuous process has been improved with each software development cycle.

Through the analysis of the survey answers about aspects of the software engineering process, agile rituals, and tools, students' points of view were identified, as well as positive aspects and suggestions. This data is important for enhancing PUMA development and the learning process.

This paper only focused on the results of Epic 1, which were prioritized through agile practices used to organize the development. Thus, other modules are also future work to be developed such as Team Building, Peer Assessment, Stakeholder Feedback, Assignment of Course Grades, Evaluation of the PBL methodology, and Alumni Follow-up.

Adoption of the functionalities outlined in this paper could be an opportunity to improve the number of real-world problems offered to students by stakeholders, and to support processes such as "Proposal Evaluation" and "Keep up with Projects", which are crucial for applying the PBL methodology.

Acknowledgment

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Foundation for Research Support of the Federal District (FAP-DF) for the financial and institutional support provided for the realization of this study, through the "FAPDF LEARNING PROGRAM," a Strategic Development Program in the macro areas of research lines: BIO Learning, TECH Learning, GOV Learning, and AGRO Learning. Their generous contribution has been essential in enabling the conduct of this research and advancing knowledge in this area of study. We recognize FAP-DF's commitment to the scientific and technological development of the region, and we are honored to have benefited from their support. We appreciate their encouragement for research and the trust placed in our work.

7 References

- Bernal, S. C. Z., Raimondi, D. C., de Oliveira, J. L. C., Inoe, K. C., & Matsuda, L. M. (2018). Práticas de identificação do paciente em unidade de terapia intensiva pediátrica. *Cogitare Enfermagem*, 23.
- Brauner, D. F., Janissek-Muniz, R., Granville, L. Z., Moura, K., Fetter, S., & Nazar, G. (2017). Experimentando a Multidisciplinaridade no Desenvolvimento de Apps. In *Anais do XXV Workshop sobre Educação em Computação*. SBC.
- Caroli, P. (2015). *Direto ao ponto: criando produtos de forma enxuta*. Editora Casa do Código.
- Cerqueira, R. J., GUIMARÃES, L. M., & Noronha, J. L. (2016). Proposta de aplicação da metodologia PBL (aprendizagem baseada em problemas) em disciplina do curso de graduação em engenharia de produção da Universidade Federal de Itajubá (UNIFEI). *Internacional Journal Active Learning*, Rio de Janeiro, 1(1), 35-55.
- De Andrade, A. G. P., dos Santos Jr, F. A. C., Pimentel, J. M., Bittencourt, J. C. N., & de Santana, T. B. (2010). Aplicação do método PBL no ensino de engenharia de software: Visão do estudante.
- Fernandes, S., Mesquita, D., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2014). Engaging students in learning: findings from a study of project-led education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 39(1), 55-67.
- Gallagher, S. A. (2023). Problem-based learning. In *Systems and models for developing programs for the gifted and talented* (pp. 193-210). Routledge.
- Gomes, R. M., Brito, E., & Varela, A. (2016). Intervenção na formação no ensino superior: a aprendizagem baseada em problemas (PBL). *Revista Interações*, 12(42).
- Betemps, C. M., Cechinel, C., & da Nóbrega Tavares, R. (2008). *Prática Integrada: Uma Abordagem Didático-Pedagógica Baseada em Projetos Colaborativos*. SBC, 167.
- Monteiro, S. B. S., Reis, A. C. B., Silva, J. M. D., & Souza, J. C. F. (2017). A Project-based Learning curricular approach in a Production Engineering Program. *Production*, 27, e20162261.
- Monteiro, S. B. S., Campos, M. R. M., Lima, A. C. F., & Melo, A. (2018). Evaluating direct and indirect results of the active methodology in learning: proposal of an integrative design in 360° via unified platform. In *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education* (Vol. 8, pp. 768-775).
- Monteiro, S. B. S., Lima, A. C. F., Mariano, A. M., & Júnior, E. S. (2020). Plataforma Unificada de Metodologia Ativa (PUMA): um projeto multidisciplinar. *Revista Ibérica de Sistemas e Tecnologias de Informação*, (E28), 766-778.
- Panke, S. (2019). Design thinking in education: Perspectives, opportunities and challenges. *Open Education Studies*, 1(1), 281-306.

- Ponciano, T. M., Gomes, F. C. D. V., & Morais, I. C. D. (2017). Metodologia ativa na engenharia: verificação da abp em uma disciplina de engenharia de produção e um modelo passo a passo.
- Schwaber, K., & Beedle, M. (2001). Agile software development with Scrum. Prentice Hall PTR.
- Sommerville, I. (2011). Engenharia de software, 9a. São Palo, SP, Brasil, 63.